

Beyond Awareness: The Mediating Role of Trust in Livestock Insurance Adoption in India

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This study investigates the psychological drivers of livestock insurance adoption among farmers in Haryana, India, focusing on how trust mediates the relationship between perceived value and behavioural intentions. Grounded in the Theory of Planned Behaviour and trust theory, the research examines small and marginal livestock farmers across six districts. Using a carefully designed survey instrument, data was collected from 270 eligible farmers with awareness of insurance schemes, following strict ethical protocols. Structural equation modeling analysis reveals that perceived value significantly enhances both trust in insurance providers and adoption intentions, while trust itself emerges as a critical factor influencing behavioural intentions. Most importantly, the findings demonstrate that trust partially mediates the impact of perceived value on farmers' willingness to adopt livestock insurance. This study shifts focus from structural barriers to psychological drivers by highlighting trust as a mediator between perceived value and adoption intention. It provides novel evidence from rural India, integrating behavioural and trust theories to explain livestock insurance uptake.

Keywords: Livestock insurance, perceived value, trust mediation, farmer behaviour, behavioural intention

The present study investigates the farmer behaviour in the context of livestock insurance adoption in the Haryana region of India. It is needless to mention that India is an agrarian economy and most of its population resides in villages and conducts agricultural and allied activities for employment (Binswanger-Mkhize, 2013). Of late, the farmers in India are facing a land availability crisis as more and more of the land is becoming fragmented making the already available land pieces smaller and unfeasible for producing and marketing the produce (Manjunatha et al., 2013; Niroula & Thapa, 2005). In most developing nations like India, farming is no longer a profitable venture for livelihood (Behera & France, 2016). Farmers face multifaceted problems because of resource constraints and this leads to their switching to alternative means of earning money (Davis, 2004). Dairy farming is one of the most profitable ventures that farmers conduct in the category of agriculture and allied activities. Rearing animals and selling their milk is a very common activity seen in almost all households of agriculturally rich state of Haryana (Kumar et al., 2015). The most common livestock are cows and buffaloes apart from sheep and goats (Numpaque et al., 2019). Here, it is noteworthy that livestock farming can be misunderstood as dairy farming only, but it is more than that and includes hen farming and many other economic activities that require animals as an active stock in the business (Buller & Roe, 2014).

Livestock farming is a cornerstone for farmers as it supports livelihoods and complements crop income. Haryana demonstrates

heavy reliance on livestock with the sector contributing 35% of agricultural GDP while supporting nearly 5 million rural households (Priya et al., 2025). Livestock farming in modern day scenario includes full-fledged commercial ventures and many academics have studied these from an entrepreneurial viewpoint (Nath et al., 2025). It has been observed that farmers often operate in an unorganized manner, leading to multiple discrepancies and uncertainties (Ullah et al., 2016). This sector is inherently full of rampant risks including epidemic and feed shortage as the common examples (Grace & McDermott, 2012). Farmers face many risks ranging from disease outbreaks to climate shocks, and it threatens their financial stability. We have already noted down that farmers face severely low per capita incomes because of the persistent issues in the farming sector and facing these risks in the alternative business models becomes a bane for them. Preventive health-checkups, keeping cash reserves, and livestock insurance are the risk management strategies to the resort of the problems arising faced by the livestock farmers (Meuwissen et al., 2001).

Livestock insurance is a rational yet underutilized risk-management tool for farmers in developing economies (Jokhio et al., 2016). In India, there are various schemes under this umbrella and studies conducted in the past indicate that farmers have due awareness of all of these schemes. These schemes include Livestock Insurance Scheme (LIS), Modified Livestock Insurance, and state-specific schemes like Gopal Ratan Yojana (Choudhury & Srinivasan, 2011). Previous literature shows that despite relatively higher awareness levels, the adoption rates remain lower because of many reasons (Choudhury & Srinivasan, 2011; Mohapatra et al., 2016). The rural population has long been wary of putting their faith in risk management and insurance practices. Farmers understand the importance of these plans for risk management and the economic benefits of livestock insurance. Trust gaps and complex documentation further impede the perceived value of the insurance schemes in the mental framework of the farmers (Giampietri et al., 2020). Despite government subsidies covering up to 50% of premiums, only 17% of eligible farmers participate in livestock insurance schemes (Mahul & Stutley, 2010).

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Many studies indicate that even when farmers recognize the economic benefits of insurance, and if there remains profound distrust in institutions, the adoption rates remain low (Cole et al., 2013). Previous studies have investigated this area from multiple perspectives but considering the psychological aspects of the farmers can be an ultimate test of the reason behind low adoption rates of livestock insurance schemes (Acharya et al., 2024). The present study advances this debate by investigating trust as a psychological mediator between farmers' perceived value of livestock insurance and their behavioural intentions in this regard. While previous research has predominantly examined structural barriers like affordability (Singh & Kaur, 2022) or awareness (Kandel & Timalisina, 2019) our conceptual model uses behavioural economics to explain intention-action gaps.

The article begins with detailed accounts of the extensive literature review conducted to establish the foundation of the study and to have an overview of the already available scientific literature related to our study. Then, the research methodology section is provided, describing the research design, development of the measurement instrument, sampling design, and data collection and analysis procedures. After this detailed mention of the research execution, the results thereof have been reported and discussed and at last, the article is concluded, giving future research directions.

Review of Literature

Perceived Value

Perceived Value is a critical determinant of decision-making and adoption behaviour, particularly in service contexts where tangible evaluations are challenging (Faqih, 2016). The construct is typically understood as the overall appraisal of a product or service's value, reflecting the trade-off between perceived gains and perceived losses (Zeithaml, 1988; Lin et al., 2005). In agricultural contexts, perceived value reflects farmers' cognitive evaluations regarding the benefits of livestock insurance relative to its cost, effort, and risk reduction potential (King & Singh, 2020). The construct was further refined by Sweeney and Soutar (2001) who highlighted aspects that affect adoption behaviour, including social, emotional and functional value. Studies in rural and insurance contexts affirm that farmers' willingness to adopt agricultural innovations largely depends on their perception of value and personal benefit (Mishra et al., 2010; Greatrex et al., 2015). Particularly for livestock insurance, perceived financial security, claim fairness, and service reliability enhance the perceived value of insurance schemes among farmers (Chantararat et al., 2013). Therefore, farmers' assessments of the total value and usefulness of livestock insurance in relation to their expectations, financial investment, and risk management needs constitute perceived value in the context of this study.

Behavioural Intention

An individual's perceived likelihood or subjective probability of engaging in a particular activity can be defined as their Behavioural Intention (Ajzen, 1991; Jackson et al., 1997). It serves as a strong predictor of actual behaviour across various domains, including technology use and service adoption (Venkatesh et al., 2003; Senali et al., 2022). In the context of livestock insurance, behavioural intention reflects farmers' willingness and readiness to enroll in insurance schemes. Prior research emphasizes that positive perceptions of value and trust significantly enhance the intention to

adopt risk-mitigating services (Hudson et al., 2017). Thus, behavioural intention represents a critical precursor to actual participation in livestock insurance programs.

Trust

Trust has long been recognized as a central element shaping human decision-making, particularly under conditions of uncertainty and perceived risk (Sarkar et al., 2020). According to the concept proposed by Mayer et al. (1995), trust may be seen as a readiness to maintain vulnerability in social relationships, based on convictions about competence, goodness and integrity of others. This psychological mechanism proves particularly significant in adoption scenarios across various domains. The importance of trust becomes even more pronounced within agricultural communities, where formal safeguards and legal protections frequently remain inadequate (Louw & Jordaan, 2016; Sikwela, 2013). When examining institutional relationships in these contexts, trust in insurance providers specifically relates to farmers' confidence that these organizations will honor commitments, maintain equitable practices, and prioritize client welfare (Ostrom & Walker, 2003). Empirical evidence strongly supports the relationship between institutional credibility and program participation rates. Multiple investigations demonstrate that enhanced perceptions of an insurance system's trustworthiness directly correlate with increased adoption among small-scale agricultural producers (Dercon et al., 2014). The underlying mechanism appears to function through two primary pathways: trust simultaneously diminishes concerns about potential transactional hazards while strengthening assurance regarding claims resolution procedures (Bao et al., 2021). For the specific purposes of this investigation, we operationalize trust as agricultural producers' confidence in the equitable practices, truthful representation, and operational reliability of livestock insurance providers. These perceptions ultimately shape their decisions regarding program enrollment and continued participation in insurance schemes.

Hypothesis Development

Relationship between Perceived Value and Trust: The expectancy-disconfirmation theory (Oliver, 1980) and institutional trust frameworks (Mayer et al., 1995) serve as the foundation for the link between perceived value and trust in livestock insurance. Farmers' perception of value encompassing cost-benefit utility (Sweeney & Soutar, 2001), risk mitigation potential (Greatrex et al., 2015), and social validation (Nguyen et al., 2024) serves as a cognitive antecedent to trust formation. When farmers evaluate livestock insurance as economically beneficial (e.g., fair premiums, timely claims), they are more likely to perceive insurers as competent, benevolent, and honest (Mayer et al., 1995) key dimensions of trust. Empirical studies in agricultural contexts support this linkage, as Cole et al. (2013) demonstrated that Indian farmers' distrust in formal financial institutions stemmed from mismatched value expectations. Based on this discussion, we propose the following hypothesis:

H1: Perceived value of livestock insurance positively influences trust in livestock insurance products among farmers in India.

Relationship between Perceived Value and Behavioural Intention

The positive relationship between perceived value and behavioural

intention is anchored in the Theory of Planned Behaviour (Ajzen, 1991) and value-adoption literature (Zeithaml, 1988). Perceived value is defined as a farmer's holistic assessment of livestock insurance products' utility relative to their costs, which serves as a critical cognitive driver of adoption intentions (Gao et al., 2023). When farmers perceive insurance as offering functional benefits, emotional reassurance, and social legitimacy, they are more likely to form positive behavioural intentions (Nordmeyer & Mußhoff, 2023). Empirical evidence supports this linkage as Li et al. (2023) found that farmers' willingness to adopt agricultural technologies correlated strongly with perceived economic returns, while Hassan (2018) demonstrated that Kenyan pastoralists' enrollment in index-based insurance was predicted by their valuation of payout reliability. In Haryana, where low perceived ROI and scheme complexity hinder uptake, emphasizing tangible value propositions could strengthen intentions. Thus, we hypothesize:

H2: Perceived value of livestock insurance positively influences the behavioural intentions of farmers to adopt livestock insurance in India.

Relationship between Trust and Behavioural Intention: Based on the Theory of Planned Behaviour (Ajzen, 1991) and the integrative model of organizational trust developed by Mayer et al. (1995) we posit that trust serves as a fundamental psychological mechanism shaping farmers' behavioural intentions toward livestock insurance adoption. Trust, defined as farmers' willingness to be vulnerable to insurers based on perceptions of competence, benevolence, and integrity (Mayer et al., 1995) reduces perceived uncertainty and enhances confidence in insurance schemes (Hosmer, 1995; Kiwanuka & Sibindi, 2025). Empirical evidence from agricultural contexts strongly supports this relationship: Dercon et al. (2014) found Ethiopian farmers' enrollment in insurance programs was primarily driven by trust in implementing institutions, while Ruml & Qaim (2021) demonstrated that distrust in claim settlement processes was the primary barrier to uptake among farmers. In the context of

Haryana, where historical grievances about claim denials and agent misconduct persist, trust becomes particularly pivotal in conversion of awareness to actual enrollment intentions. The behavioural economics literature further substantiates this linkage, showing that trust lowers mental transaction costs and mitigates present bias (Beerbaum et al., 2019). When farmers trust insurers to honor contracts and act in their best interest, they exhibit stronger intentions to: (1) enroll livestock, (2) renew policies, and (3) advocate for insurance within their social networks (Hudson et al., 2017). Thus, we hypothesize:

H3: Trust in livestock insurance products positively influences the behavioural intentions of farmers to adopt livestock insurance in India.

Mediating Role of Trust: Building on the Theory of Planned Behaviour (Ajzen, 1991) and trust-based adoption models (Mayer et al., 1995) we propose that trust mediates the perceived value-behavioural intention relationship. Farmers' valuation of insurance (cost-benefit utility, risk reduction) first cultivates trust in insurers' competence and integrity (Dragos et al., 2023; Smith, 2016) which then strengthens adoption intentions. Empirical studies confirm this indirect pathway: In Kenya, insurers' transparency increased both trust and enrollment (Jensen et al., 2021) while Aheeyar et al. (2019) found that distrust undermined impact of perceived value. Given the above discussion, we hypothesize:

H4: Trust in livestock insurance products mediates the relationship between perceived value of livestock insurance and behavioural intentions of farmers to adopt livestock insurance in India.

Proposed Conceptual Framework: The study's conceptual model outlines the proposed connections among the three main constructs: Behavioural Intention, Perceived Value and Trust. Trust and Behavioural Intention are directly positively influenced by Perceived Value, which is positioned as a key antecedent. Trust, in turn, is theorized to positively affect Behavioural Intention, reflecting its critical role in shaping farmers' willingness to adopt livestock insurance. Additionally, Trust is posited to mediate the relationship between Perceived Value and Behavioural Intention, suggesting that the influence of perceived benefits and worth of livestock insurance on adoption intentions partly operates through the development of trust in insurance providers.

Figure 1

Proposed Conceptual Model

Note. Source: The Authors

This structure aligns with the theoretical foundations of the Theory of Planned Behaviour and trust-based adoption models, emphasizing both cognitive evaluation and relational confidence as drivers of behavioural outcomes. The model is depicted in a horizontal, linear format for clarity, with each construct represented as an oval and the directional paths shown as straight arrows. This visual arrangement highlights the sequential and mediated nature of the hypothesized relationships, facilitating an intuitive understanding of the conceptual framework guiding the study and serving as the basis for the formulation of hypotheses and subsequent empirical analysis.

Method

Measurement Instrument Development

The creation of a questionnaire that functions as both a data collection tool and a measurement tool comes next in survey-based research when the study design is complete. To test the proposed research model and underlying hypotheses, we developed a structured questionnaire based on a comprehensive review of existing literature. This review aimed to identify validated scales that have been widely used to measure the variables of interest: Perceived Value, Trust, and Behavioural Intention in the context of livestock insurance.

Perceived Value was measured using four items adapted from Sweeney and Soutar (2001) focusing on aspects like value-for-money, worth of benefits, and financial security. Example items include, “*Livestock insurance provides good value for money*” and “*The benefits I receive from livestock insurance are worth the cost.*” Trust was measured using three items adapted from Mayer and Davis (1999) assessing trustworthiness and reliability. A sample item includes, “*I believe livestock insurance providers are honest in their dealings with farmers.*” Behavioural Intention was measured using three items adapted from Venkatesh et al. (2003) focusing on future intent and encouragement. Example items include, “*I intend*

Table 1
Measurement Items and Sources

Variable	Item Code	Measurement Statements	Source(s)
Perceived Value	PV1	Livestock insurance provides good value for money.	Sweeney & Soutar (2001)
	Pv2	The benefits I receive from livestock insurance are worth the cost.	Sweeney & Soutar (2001)
	PV3	Overall, I consider livestock insurance a worthwhile investment.	Sweeney & Soutar (2001)
	PV3	Livestock insurance improves my financial security significantly.	Sweeney & Soutar (2001)
Trust	T1	I believe livestock insurance providers are honest in their dealings with farmers.	Mayer & Davis (1999)
	T2	I trust livestock insurance providers to act in my best interest.	Mayer & Davis (1999)
	T3	Livestock insurance providers fulfill their promises made to farmers.	Mayer & Davis (1999)
Behavioural Intention	BI1	I intend to enroll my livestock under insurance policies in the future.	Venkatesh et al. (2003)
	BI2	I will encourage other farmers to adopt livestock insurance.	Venkatesh et al. (2003)
	BI3	I plan to regularly insure my livestock.	Venkatesh et al. (2003)

Note. Source: Literature review

to enroll my livestock under insurance policies in the future” and “I will encourage other farmers to adopt livestock insurance.” Table 1 presents the measurement items and their respective sources.

The questionnaire also included demographic data such as age, gender, industry type, work experience, and organizational tenure, divided into two parts. The first part collected demographic information, while the second part contained items related to the constructs under study. Each item was measured using a 5-point Likert scale (1 = *Strongly Disagree*, 5 = *Strongly Agree*). To minimize common method bias and ensure the instrument's robustness, a pilot study with a sample of 30 participants was conducted.

Data Collection and Analysis

After the finalization of the survey instrument, the sampling design was framed, and data collection was conducted. Any farmer engaged in livestock rearing activities in the rural regions of Haryana, India, was eligible to participate in the present study. The survey was administered across key districts of Haryana known for livestock farming, including Hisar, Karnal, Jind, Kaithal, Rohtak, and Bhiwani. To maintain the relevance of our study, farmers without any awareness or exposure to livestock insurance schemes were excluded. The primary focus was on small and marginal farmers involved in cattle, buffalo, and goat rearing. Ethical considerations were strictly followed, ensuring confidentiality and voluntary participation. The survey adhered to scientific guidelines to enhance data reliability and minimize common method bias. Surveys were distributed using both in-person interviews and offline questionnaires to maximize response rates. A total of 350 questionnaires were distributed, yielding 274 completed responses. After data cleaning, 4 responses were eliminated, and the remaining 270 responses were used for analysis.

Statistical Analysis

The present study employed structural equation modeling to examine the impact of Perceived Value on Behavioural Intention toward livestock insurance schemes through the mediating role of Trust. The statistical packages and software used were SPSS and SmartPLS. The following sections present the results and findings derived from the analysis.

Results

Participants

Table 2 presents the demographic profile of the respondents. The

sample comprises 270 farmers, with a significant majority being male (82.2%), while females constitute 17.8%. The age distribution shows that most respondents fall within the 30-40 years category (34.8%), followed by those aged 41-50 years (30.4%), above 50 years (21.5%), and below 30 years (13.3%). In terms of educational qualifications, the majority have completed education up to the 10th standard (40.7%), followed by those who completed 12th standard (34.1%), and a smaller proportion (25.2%) who have attained graduation and above qualifications. Regarding farming experience, the largest segment has 6-10 years of experience (32.6%), followed by 11-15 years (27.4%), more than 15 years (24.4%), and 1-5 years (15.6%).

Table 2

Demographic Profiles of Respondents

Demographic Trait	Category	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Gender	Male	222	82.2%
	Female	48	17.8%
Age Group	Below 30 years	36	13.3%
	30-40 years	94	34.8%
	41-50 years	82	30.4%
	Above 50 years	58	21.5%
Educational Qualification	Up to 10th standard	110	40.7%
	12th standard	92	34.1%
	Graduation and above	68	25.2%
Farming Experience	1-5 years	42	15.6%
	6-10 years	88	32.6%
	11-15 years	74	27.4%
	More than 15 years	66	24.4%
Farm Size	Small-scale (<5 acres)	112	41.5%
	Medium-scale (5-15 acres)	105	38.9%
	Large-scale (>15 acres)	53	19.6%

Note. Source(s): Survey data collected by authors

In terms of farm size, a substantial portion of respondents are engaged in small-scale farming (41.5%), followed by medium-scale farmers (38.9%) and large-scale farmers (19.6%). These demographic details provide a comprehensive understanding of the sample composition, ensuring diversity in gender, age, education, farming experience, and farm size, thereby enhancing the robustness and generalizability of the study findings.

Assessment of Measurement Model

Following the use of the data screening procedure suggested by Hair et al. (2019) the measurement model (outer model) and structural model (inner model) were tested. Partial least squares structural equation modeling (PLS-SEM) was utilized to evaluate both the measurement model and the structural model. For the measurement model, assessment criteria were based on reliability and validity, as

detailed in Table 3 and Figure 2. Reliability was determined through indicator reliability and further supported by internal consistency measures, namely composite reliability (CR) and Henseler's rhoA, which exceeded the standard cutoff of 0.70 (Hair et al., 2019; Hair & Alamer, 2022). Convergent validity was validated by ensuring the average variance extracted (AVE) was greater than 0.50 (Hair & Alamer, 2022).

Table 3
Constructs' Reliability and Validity

Constructs	Indicators	Loadings	Cronbach's Alpha	rhoA	Composite Reliability	AVE
Perceived Value	PV1	0.864	0.905	0.911	0.936	0.745
	PV2	0.878				
	PV3	0.854				
	PV4	0.832				
Trust	T1	0.860	0.885	0.892	0.922	0.748
	T2	0.873				
	T3	0.843				
Behavioural Intention	BI1	0.868	0.878	0.884	0.917	0.736
	BI2	0.850				
	BI3	0.841				

Note. Source(s): Authors' own data analysis

Figure 2
Research Model

Note. Source: SmartPLS

Discriminant Validity

The next step in assessing the outer model is to establish discriminant validity, which was evaluated using the Fornell-Larcker criterion. This approach compares the square root of the AVE values for each construct with inter-construct correlation values (Fornell & Larcker, 1981). As shown in Table 4, the square root of the AVE for each construct exceeds its highest correlation with any other construct, thereby confirming discriminant validity.

Additionally, to support the evaluation of discriminant validity, the Heterotrait-Monotrait Ratio (HTMT) criterion was used (Henseler et al., 2015). All HTMT values remained below the crucial threshold of 0.85, indicating that each construct is conceptually

unique. Thus, Table 4 and 5 report that the discriminant validity is successfully established using both the HTMT and the Fornell-Larcker criteria.

Table 4
Discriminant Validity using the Fornell-Larcker Criterion

Constructs	PV	Trust	BI
Perceived Value	0.863		
Trust	0.618	0.865	
Behavioural Intention (BI)	0.602	0.631	0.871

Note(s). PV = Perceived Value, BI = Behavioural Intention, Source(s): Authors' own data analysis

Table 5*Discriminant Validity using the HTMT Criterion*

Constructs	PV	Trust	BI
Perceived Value			
Trust	0.673		
Behavioural Intention (BI)	0.651	0.701	

Note(s). PV = Perceived Value, BI = Behavioural Intention, Source(s): Authors' own data analysis

Hypothesis Testing

Collinearity was studied before evaluating the structural model (Hair

& Alamer, 2022). Analysis of the Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) data revealed that all indicators remained below the permissible threshold, with the higher VIF value observed being 1.213 (Hair et al., 2019). To examine the significance of path coefficients, the bootstrapping method was applied with 10,000 subsamples (Hair & Alamer, 2022). The results indicate that Perceived Value positively influences Trust ($\beta = 0.428, p < 0.000$), thus supporting H1. Similarly, Perceived Value positively influences Behavioural Intention ($\beta = 0.332, p < 0.000$), supporting H2. Additionally, Trust positively influences Behavioural Intention ($\beta = 0.297, p < 0.000$), supporting H3.

Table 6*Results of Structural Model*

Relationships	Std. Beta	p-value	t-value	BC 95% CI	Significance	f-square	VIF
H1 PV → T	0.428	0.000	8.437	[0.314; 0.523]	Yes	0.200	1.000
H2 PV → BI	0.332	0.000	5.689	[0.203; 0.430]	Yes	0.110	1.213
H3 T → BI	0.297	0.000	4.968	[0.164; 0.390]	Yes	0.087	1.196
Mediation Analysis							
H4 PV → T → BI	0.127	0.000	4.021	[0.068; 0.189]	Yes		

Note(s): PV = Perceived Value, T = Trust, BI = Behavioural Intention, Source: Authors' own data analysis.

The study also examined mediation effects, revealing that Trust mediates the relationship between Perceived Value and Behavioural Intention ($\beta = 0.127, p < 0.000$), supporting H4. These findings indicate how significant Perceived Value and Trust are in determining farmers' inclinations to get livestock insurance. Table 6 presents the results of the detailed Structural Model.

Discussion

Practical Implications of the Study

The findings of this study provide important practical insights for insurance providers, policymakers, and rural development agencies seeking to enhance livestock insurance adoption among farmers. The results reveal that perceived value significantly strengthens trust, which in turn increases farmers' behavioural intentions to adopt livestock insurance. This finding aligns with earlier studies suggesting that farmers are more willing to engage with insurance schemes when they perceive clear economic and risk-mitigation benefits (Chantarat et al., 2013; King & Singh, 2020). Perceived value in terms of financial security, fairness of premiums, and reliability of compensation enhances farmers' confidence in insurance products, thereby encouraging participation. Consistent with prior evidence, this study confirms that trust plays a decisive role in shaping adoption intentions in agricultural insurance contexts (Dercon et al., 2014; Giampietri et al., 2020). Farmers who trust insurance providers are more likely to overcome concerns related to claim settlement delays, administrative complexity, and perceived opportunism. Similar findings have been reported by Bao et al. (2021) who observed that trust significantly motivates farmers to purchase disaster insurance by reducing uncertainty and perceived transactional risk.

From a policy perspective, the findings highlight the need to design insurance schemes that visibly enhance farmers' perceived value while simultaneously strengthening institutional trust.

Simplifying claim procedures, ensuring timely payouts, and maintaining transparent communication can significantly improve farmers' confidence, as suggested by Cole et al. (2013) and Ruml and Qaim (2021). Practical interventions such as village-level awareness workshops, farmer-centric grievance redressal mechanisms, and the involvement of trusted local intermediaries can further reinforce trust and participation. Additionally, the study suggests that insurance literacy programs embedded within existing agricultural extension initiatives can play a critical role in improving adoption. Previous research indicates that limited understanding of insurance mechanisms often weakens perceived value and trust, particularly among small and marginal farmers (Mahul & Stutley, 2010; Kandel & Timalina, 2019). By emphasizing tangible benefits and fair practices, policymakers and insurers can promote sustained engagement with livestock insurance schemes, contributing to farmers' financial resilience and rural economic stability.

Theoretical Implications of the Study

This study contributes to the existing literature by empirically demonstrating the interlinked roles of perceived value and trust in shaping farmers' behavioural intentions toward livestock insurance adoption. Drawing on the Theory of Planned Behaviour (Ajzen, 1991) and trust-based frameworks (Mayer et al., 1995) the findings confirm that cognitive evaluations of value serve as a crucial antecedent to trust formation, which subsequently influences behavioural intention. This supports earlier conceptual assertions that trust functions as a psychological mechanism through which value perceptions are translated into action (Giampietri et al., 2020; Dragos et al., 2023). Importantly, the study extends the application of value-based adoption theories, traditionally used in technology and service research, to the domain of agricultural insurance. While prior studies have applied perceived usefulness and ease-of-use constructs primarily in technological contexts (Venkatesh et al., 2003) the present findings demonstrate that perceived value is

equally relevant in explaining adoption behaviour in non-technological, risk-intensive environments. This corroborates emerging evidence suggesting that perceived value significantly influences adoption decisions in agricultural and rural service settings (Gao et al., 2023; Nordmeyer & Mußhoff, 2023). Furthermore, the confirmed mediating role of trust adds theoretical depth to existing insurance adoption models. While previous research has largely focused on socio-economic constraints, affordability, or awareness as primary determinants (Mohapatra et al., 2016; Singh & Kaur, 2022) this study positions trust as a central psychological conduit linking perceived value and behavioural intention. This finding resonates with studies by Jensen et al. (2021) and Bao et al. (2021) which emphasize trust as a decisive factor in reducing intention-action gaps in insurance participation. By highlighting trust as a mediator, the study advances theoretical understanding of behavioural decision-making in rural insurance contexts and calls for future research to explore additional moderating variables such as prior claim experience, social influence, and institutional transparency. Integrating these factors may help develop more comprehensive behavioural frameworks that capture the cognitive, relational, and contextual dimensions influencing farmers' participation in livestock insurance programs.

Conclusion and Future Research Directions

This study highlights the significant role of Perceived Value in enhancing Trust and promoting behavioural intention toward livestock insurance schemes among rural farmers. The findings suggest that when farmers perceive livestock insurance as valuable and beneficial, it fosters greater trust in insurance providers, which in turn strengthens their intention to participate in such schemes. While this study provides valuable insights, several limitations should be acknowledged that present opportunities for further investigation. An important consideration is that while the current research demonstrates connections between Perceived Value, Trust, and Behavioural Intention, there remains a need for longitudinal examination. Future work should track how trust and value perceptions develop across time and how these changes affect continued participation in insurance programs. Such extended observation would provide more robust evidence about the lasting impacts of these psychological factors. Further research avenues could productively investigate additional variables that might moderate or mediate these relationships. Factors worth exploring include previous claim experiences of farmers, social influences within communities, education levels, and the transparency of insurance schemes. Examining these elements would offer a more comprehensive understanding of the psychological processes underlying adoption decisions. The potential influence of external support systems also merits attention. Future studies could assess how government assistance programs and technology-based solutions affect the development of trust and perceptions of value among farmers. Understanding these dynamics would help evaluate the effectiveness of such interventions. This research makes an important contribution to agricultural risk management literature by highlighting the crucial role of psychological and trust-related factors in livestock insurance adoption.

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